

Definition.

The *concept “without prejudice”* is a form of legal privilege¹ aimed at protecting the disclosure of communications and documents prepared in connection with, and for the purpose of, settlement negotiations. This privilege ensures a candid, free, and uninhibited flow of information between parties during their settlement discussions², by rendering the content to which it is attached inadmissible at trial.³ Without prejudice correspondences, statements, or communications made during settlement negotiations or ADR proceedings with the aim of reaching a settlement agreement between disputing parties are generally privileged. Therefore, they should not be admitted as evidence in subsequent arbitration or court proceedings.⁴ For this privilege to apply, there must be an actual dispute and a genuine attempt to settle it. It is not enough for parties to merely discuss how an admitted liability is to be paid. Commercial discussions about such matters, even when one party seeks a concession from the other regarding payment terms, do not qualify for without prejudice protection.⁵

Conclusively defined by Berger, *“Statements, views, admissions, proposals, suggestions, indications of readiness to accept a certain proposal for settlement, whether written or oral, submitted by a party during settlement negotiations, mediation/conciliation or any other ADR proceedings, or statements made or views expressed by a third neutral involved in such proceedings, and any document, witness statement and expert report submitted in or prepared solely for these negotiations or stemming from settlement negotiations, mediation/conciliation or any other ADR process between the parties are inadmissible as evidence in subsequent arbitration*

¹ Edward William Phipson. *Phipson on Evidence*, eighteenth edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell Ltd., December 2013. Paragraph 24-09.

² Klaus Peter Berger. “The Settlement Privilege: A General Principle of International Alternative Dispute Resolution Law.” *Arbitration International*, Volume 24, Number 2 (1 June 2008): pages 265–281, at page 274.

³ David Foskett. *The Law and Practice of Compromise: With Precedents*, seventh revised edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell, 2010. Paragraph 19-04.

⁴ Berger, *supra note*. 2.

⁵ *Bradford & Bingley plc (Appellant) v Rashid (Respondent)* [2006] United Kingdom House of Lords 37; (2006) 1 *Weekly Law Reports* 2066 at paragraphs 72–73 and 83.

or court proceedings between the same parties, provided that the privilege objection is raised in the arbitration or court proceedings in good faith and does not relate to facts which one side would have been able to prove had there been no settlement negotiations”.

Origin.

Without Prejudice offer originates as the earliest cases to which reference continues to be made from time to time are cases derived from the late 18th century⁶. *Waldrige v Kennison (1794) 1 Esp. 142 and Turner v Railton (1796) 2 Esp. 474, both cases in which the views of Lord Kenyon C.J. are recorded.*

The sanctity of this privilege to such 'without prejudice' exchanges in common law jurisdictions can be traced back in history to an English Case of 'Walker v. Wilsher'⁷, of 1889.1 In this case defendants tried to use the 'without prejudice' communications for depriving the plaintiffs of the costs and were successful at the court of first instance. But in the appeal, it was set aside.⁸

The court, specifically **Lord Justice Bowen**, emphasized the importance of protecting such exchanges to encourage compromise. He stated, *"In my opinion it would be a bad thing and lead to serious consequences if the Courts allowed the action of litigants, on letters written to them without prejudice, to be given in evidence against them or to be used as material for depriving them of costs. It is most important that the door should not be shut against compromises, as would certainly be the case if letters written without prejudice and suggesting methods of compromise were liable to be read when a question of costs arose. The agreement that the letter is without prejudice ought, I think, to be carried out in its full integrity."*

⁶ David Foskett. *The Law and Practice of Compromise: With Precedents*, seventh revised edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell, 2010. Paragraph 18-02.

⁷ Walker v Wilsher (1889) *Law Reports, Queen's Bench Division* 23 at 335.

⁸ Jayems Dhingra. "It Is Time to Unseal Sealed Offers in International Arbitration: As a Negotiation Strategy or Pressure Tactics?" *Arbitration International*, Volume 28, Number 3 (2012): pages 511–532. © London Court of International Arbitration.

Criteria & Landmark Case laws.

Landmark Case Laws. Several key cases have shaped and defined the application of **without prejudice** privilege, emphasizing the underlying public policy⁹ of encouraging settlements and protecting negotiation efforts from later disclosure.

1. **Walker v Wilsher (1889) 23 QBD 335**

In this case defendants tried to use the 'without prejudice' communications for depriving the plaintiffs of the costs and were successful at the court of first instance. But in the appeal it was set aside. This case established one of the earliest foundations for the **without prejudice** rule in English law. Lord Justice Bowen emphasized¹⁰ that "it would lead to serious consequences" if communications labeled "without prejudice" could later be used as evidence. The case reaffirmed the principle that protecting settlement discussions is crucial to maintaining open and honest negotiations "*It is most important that the door should not be shut against compromises*".

2. **Rush & Tompkins Ltd v Greater London Council [1989] 1 A.C. 1280**

In this case, the primary legal issue revolved around the "**without prejudice**" privilege in correspondence. The plaintiffs, Rush & Tompkins Ltd., entered into a settlement with the Greater London Council (G.L.C.) following a building contract dispute. The second defendants, P. J. Carey Plant Hire (Oval) Ltd., sought discovery of the "without prejudice" correspondence between the plaintiffs and the G.L.C., arguing that the privilege should not apply once a settlement was reached. It extended the rule beyond mere admissions to cover all negotiations aimed at settling disputes. The House of Lords held that any communications made with a view to resolving a dispute were inadmissible, regardless of whether a settlement

⁹ Norah Gallagher. "Legal Privileges in International Arbitration." *International Arbitration Law Review*, Volume 6, 2003: page 45 at 48: 'there is no minimum international standard that can be applied'; "*Under English law, any written or oral communication made for the purpose of 'a genuine attempt to compromise a dispute between the parties' is subject to the 'without prejudice' privilege.*"

¹⁰ Jayems Dhingra. "It Is Time to Unseal Sealed Offers in International Arbitration: As a Negotiation Strategy or Pressure Tactics?" *Arbitration International*, Volume 28, Number 3 (2012): pages 511–532. © London Court of International Arbitration.

was reached. This case confirmed that the rule applied not just to admissions but to all settlement-related discussions, a significant broadening of its scope.

3. Bradford & Bingley Plc v Rashid [2006] 1 W.L.R. 2066

In this case, the House of Lords clarified that the **without prejudice** rule does not apply to communications concerning the repayment of admitted liabilities. The court held that because there was no dispute over the liability itself—only over how it would be repaid—such discussions did not qualify for protection under the privilege. This case covers key references when differentiating between negotiations over disputed liabilities versus admitted liabilities.

4. P. T. Tri-M.G. Intra Asia Airlines v. Norse Air Charter Limited [2009] SGHC 13¹¹

This case reinforced the distinction between **admissions of interest** made during genuine settlement negotiations, which are protected, and **admissions of liability**, which are not. It highlighted the importance of ensuring that the parties are attempting to settle a genuine dispute for the privilege to apply (Findings).

5. Motorola Solutions Inc v Hytera Communications Corp Ltd [2021] EWCA Civ 114

In this case, the Court of Appeal emphasized that the **without prejudice** privilege could be set aside in cases of "unambiguous impropriety." This case illustrates the exception to the rule, allowing the court to consider otherwise privileged communications where there is clear evidence of misconduct during negotiations. The Court of Appeal has held that the narrow "unambiguous impropriety"¹² exception to without prejudice privilege, which permits courts

¹¹ *P. T. Tri-M.G. Intra Asia Airlines v. Norse Air Charter Limited*, Judgment of the High Court of Singapore [2009] SGHC 13, 12 January 2009, para. 59-63. "Without prejudice" privilege only serves to protect admissions of interest made in the course of settlement negotiations so as to promote out-of-court settlement of disputes. That is to be distinguished from admissions of liability where the privilege does not attach: see *Greenline-Onyx Envirotech Phils, Inc v Otto Systems Singapore Pte Ltd* [2007] 3 SLR 40 at [16] – [19] and *Sin Lian Heng Construction Pte Ltd v Singapore Telecommunications Ltd* [2007] 2 SLR 433 at [41] and [45] ("*Sin Lian Heng*"). ¹¹ "Without prejudice" privilege. Such privilege attaches to negotiations to settle genuine disputes over quantum even if there had been an admission as to liability. I am satisfied that those emails were exchanged in the context of negotiations on settlement and that to allow the adduction of such evidence would patently undermine the policy of encouraging out-of-court settlements. It is therefore not open to me to find that there had been an admission as to quantum."

¹² Will be examined as an exception to the Without Prejudice privilege below.

to admit evidence of settlement discussions where a party has abused the protection of the privilege, is to be applied only where there is clear evidence of impropriety¹³.

6. Oceanbulk Shipping & Trading SA v TMT Asia Ltd [2011] 1 A.C. 662

The UK Supreme Court in this case held that **without prejudice** communications can be admitted in evidence where they are relevant to the construction of a contract that followed from the negotiations. This case expanded the exceptions to the rule, showing that the courts may admit **without prejudice** communications to interpret contracts. the Supreme Court held that without prejudice material was potentially admissible as part of the factual matrix for the purposes of construing a contract concluded after without prejudice discussions¹⁴.

Key Criteria for Application.

It should be established that these criteria are neither exhaustive nor derived from a single source. Rather, they represent a conclusion drawn from multiple case analyses and scholarly opinions. However, for communications to fall under the protection of the **without prejudice** privilege, certain **criteria** must be satisfied. These criteria ensure that only those *communications genuinely aimed at settling disputes*¹⁵ are protected from being used as evidence:

1. Existence of a Dispute
a **genuine dispute** must exist between the parties at the time the communication is made. The privilege will not attach to communications concerning how an admitted liability should be paid or discussions related to matters *where no dispute exists*. This distinction was reinforced in *P. T. Tri-M.G. Intra Asia Airlines v. Norse Air Charter Limited [2009] SGHC 13*, where the court clarified that the privilege "only serves to protect admissions of interest made during settlement negotiations" and not admissions of liability. Similarly, in *Bradford & Bingley Plc*

¹³ Motorola Solutions, Incorporated and another v Hytera Communications Corporation Limited and another (Revised Judgment 1) [2021] England and Wales Court of Appeal (Civil Division) 11 (11 January 2021).

¹⁴ Edward William Phipson. *Phipson on Evidence*, eighteenth edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell Ltd., December 2013, Pp. 111-112.

¹⁵ Herrmann, Gerold, "Commentary on the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law Conciliation Rules," *Yearbook on Commercial Arbitration*, Volume 6 (1981): 170–190, at 189: 'ensure settlement efforts by the parties unimpeded by any fear of later disadvantages in other proceedings.'

v. Rashid [2006] UKHL 37, the court found that communications discussing repayment of admitted debts did not qualify for protection under the **without prejudice** rule.

2. Genuine Attempt to Resolve the Dispute

Fundamentally, the communication must represent a **genuine attempt** to resolve the dispute. This was affirmed in *Sin Lian Heng Construction Pte Ltd v Singapore Telecommunications Ltd [2007] 2 SLR 433*, where the Singapore Court of Appeal held that the privilege attaches only when the communication is intended to negotiate a settlement. If the communication is merely commercial in nature or about the logistics of payment (without attempts at compromise), it will not be protected by the privilege. Similarly in *Georgia Corporation v. Gavino*¹⁶ **Supplies the court found that** Commercial discussions to that end, even when one party seeks a concession from the other as to payment of the liability, generally do not qualify for such privilege. Such ruling also aligned with *Bradford & Bingley plc v Rashid*¹⁷ .

3. Privileged Communication Must Be Made for Settlement Purposes

As affirmed in *Rush & Tompkins Ltd v Greater London Council [1989] 1 A.C. 1280*, the privilege applies to any communication made with a view to settling a dispute. The court ruled that the rule applies regardless of *whether the settlement is eventually reached or not*, provided the communication is made for that purpose. Similarly, in *Unilever plc v The Procter & Gamble Co [2000] 1 WLR 2436*, the Court of Appeal ruled that the privilege applies broadly to all communications made in the context of settlement negotiations¹⁸. Lastly, Even if statements are not expressed to be 'without prejudice', privilege will still attach, if in substance they

¹⁶ *Georgia Corporation v. Gavino Supplies (UAE) Fze*, Judgment of the Court of First Instance of the Dubai International Financial Centre Courts [2016] DIFC ARB 005, 11 October 2016, para. 36

¹⁷ *Bradford & Bingley plc (Appellant) v Rashid (Respondent)* [2006] United Kingdom House of Lords 37; (2006) 1 *Weekly Law Reports* 2066 at paragraphs 72–73 and 83.

¹⁸ *Rochester Resources Limited v. Coral Petroleum Limited*, Judgment of the High Court of Justice of England and Wales [2014] EWHC 2185, 20 June 2014, para. 35.

constitute a genuine attempt to reach a compromise¹⁹, titles and labels of the documents are irrelevant in that context.

Exceptions to the Without Prejudice Privilege.

there are recognized **exceptions** where courts or tribunals may admit such communications into evidence:

1. Fraud, Misrepresentation, or Impropriety

The **without prejudice** privilege does not protect communications where there is clear evidence of misconduct such as fraud, misrepresentation, or other forms of **unambiguous impropriety**. This exception was highlighted in *Unilever plc v Procter & Gamble Co [2000] 1 WLR 2436*, where the court allowed evidence of settlement negotiations because it was alleged that the other party had engaged in improper conduct. Similarly, in *Motorola Solutions Inc v Hytera Communications Corp Ltd [2021] EWCA Civ 114*, the Court of Appeal reaffirmed that settlement communications may be admitted where there is clear evidence of threats or blackmail during negotiations (Findings).

The expression “unambiguous impropriety”²⁰ is a convenient generic description applied to a variety of things said or done during without prejudice negotiations which may, in certain circumstances, be admitted in evidence. It was first used by Hoffmann L.J. in *Forster v Friedland*²¹ and has since become part of the legal lexicon in this context. the “without

¹⁹ Erich Suter, “Discrimination Without Prejudice: Woodward v Santander United Kingdom Plc,” *Arbitration: The International Journal of Arbitration, Mediation and Dispute Management*, Volume 77, Issue 1 (2011): pages 147–154. Reprinted by Sweet & Maxwell,: ‘The tide on top of the document or communication ‘without prejudice’ does not automatically grant the privilege under ‘without prejudice’ rule. The communications which relate to a debt outstanding and where there is no dispute about it, then ‘without prejudice’ rule can’t be applied. ’; Berger *supra* note 2, p. 267; John A. Tackaberry, “General Principles,” in Ronald Bernstein (editor), *Handbook of Arbitration Practice*, fourth edition (London: Sweet & Maxwell in conjunction with the Chartered Institute of Arbitrators, 30 October 2003), page 158.

²⁰ David Foskett. *The Law and Practice of Compromise: With Precedents*, seventh revised edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell, 2010. Paragraph 19-39.

²¹ In *Unilever Plc v The Procter & Gamble Company* (England and Wales Court of Appeal, Civil Division, 28 October 1999), Robert Walker L.J. identified an exception to the general rule as being one where “one party may be allowed

prejudice” label may be disregarded by the court, Lord Griffiths in *Rush & Tompkins Ltd v GLC* referred to the case of *Kitcat v Sharp*²² as authority for the proposition that a threat will not be subject to the privilege. In fact that case involved letters written by a defendant to a clergyman plaintiff, marked “private and confidential”, in which he threatened to publish the statement of claim with his abusive marginal comments appended to it to, amongst others, the plaintiff’s bishop. Vaver²³ draws attention to two Commonwealth cases where threats, lack of good faith and abuse of the rule led the court to disregard the without prejudice tag, In his commentary on these two cases, Vaver says this: “*Compromises are regularly induced by such considerations as the desire to preserve good relations between the parties (especially if they are commercial men), the supposed weaknesses of a party’s case, the supposed strength of the opponent’s case, the costs and risks of litigation, etc. These are part and parcel of settlements in everyday life. On the other hand, misrepresentations, libels, threats of insolvency or bankruptcy in the event of non-acceptance, blackmail, threats of perjury, suborning or flight from the jurisdiction must all amount to the sort of improper pressure which ought to be admitted in evidence if relevant to some matter in issue—this notwithstanding they occur during ‘without prejudice’ negotiations.*”²⁴

2. Concluded Settlement Agreement

If there is a dispute about whether a **settlement agreement** has been concluded between the parties, **without prejudice** communications may be admitted to determine whether the parties reached an agreement. This exception is rooted in the need to resolve ambiguity over the

to give evidence of what the other said or wrote in without prejudice negotiations if the exclusion of the evidence would act as a cloak for perjury, blackmail or other ‘unambiguous impropriety’

22 *Kitcat v Sharp* [1882] Law Times Reports 48, 64 (Justice Fry).

23 Vaver, Michael W., “Without Prejudice Privilege”, *University of British Columbia Law Review* (June 1974): 85, 152–153.

24 For more, see *Muller v Linsley & Mortimer* [1996] Professional Negligence and Liability Reports, Volume 1, 74 at 79–80. The judgment was agreed with by Swinton Thomas and Leggatt L.JJ. The analysis did not purport to deal with the exception based upon the revelation of “unambiguous impropriety” perpetrated during without prejudice negotiations: Hoffmann L.J. referred to in *Forster v Friedland* (1992) CAT 1052.

finality of settlement discussions. In *Oceanbulk Shipping & Trading SA v TMT Asia Ltd*²⁵, the UK Supreme Court held that without prejudice material was potentially admissible as part of the factual matrix for the purposes of construing a contract concluded after without prejudice discussions²⁶.

3. Waiver by Conduct or Agreement

The **without prejudice** protection can be **waived** if the parties explicitly agree to lift the privilege or if a party's conduct amounts to an unequivocal act of waiver. For example, in *Seventh Earl of Malmesbury v Strutt & Parker*, the parties agreed that settlement offers made during mediation could be disclosed during the determination of costs, which led to the privilege being lifted for that purpose²⁷. Waiver can also occur through **inconsistent conduct**²⁸, where a party attempts to rely on **without prejudice** material selectively, as noted in *Somatra Ltd v Sinclair Roche & Temperley*²⁹.

²⁵ *Oceanbulk Shipping & Trading SA v TMT Asia Limited and others* [2010] United Kingdom Supreme Court 44; [2011] 1 Appeal Cases 662.

²⁶ Edward William Phipson. *Phipson on Evidence*, eighteenth edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell Ltd., December 2013, Pp. 111-112.

²⁷ Jayems Dhingra. "It Is Time to Unseal Sealed Offers in International Arbitration: As a Negotiation Strategy or Pressure Tactics?" *Arbitration International*, Volume 28, Number 3 (2012): pages 511–532. © London Court of International Arbitration.

²⁸ David Foskett. *The Law and Practice of Compromise: With Precedents*, seventh revised edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell, 2010. Paragraph 18-01.

²⁹ In *Somatra Ltd v Sinclair Roche & Temperley* [2000] 1 WLR 2453 at 2465 (Court of Appeal), where Clarke L.J., as he then was, said: "[W]here, in support of its case on the merits of an action, a party deploys material which would not be admissible because it forms part of without prejudice communications the other party is entitled to refer to the contents of those same communications in order to advance its own case on the merits. It does not seem to me to be just to allow the first party to obtain an advantage by relying on the without prejudice material in one part of the litigation, as here on an application for Mareva relief, where the merits are relevant, and to rely upon the without prejudice nature of the communications when the other party wished to rely upon, say, an admission made in the same without prejudice discussions at the trial, where the merits are of course also relevant." He had previously said: "It seems to me that no party which has taken part in without prejudice discussions should be entitled to use them to his advantage on the merits of the case in one context but then assert a right to prevent its opponent from doing so on the merits at the trial."

4. **Estoppel**³⁰, Without prejudice communications may be admitted where a party’s statement in such communications gives rise to **estoppel**. If one party relies on the statements or representations made during settlement discussions and alters their position accordingly, the privilege may be lifted to prevent unfairness. This exception was recognized in *Bradford & Bingley Plc v Rashid* [2006] 1 WLR 2066, where the court held that the privilege could not be invoked to prevent the use of **without prejudice** material in situations where it would otherwise cause injustice.
5. **Costs** Another key exception is where **without prejudice** communications are marked “**without prejudice save as to costs**”. This allows the court or tribunal to consider those communications when deciding on costs, but not on the substantive merits of the case. Such communications, often referred to as **Calderbank offers**, can influence cost decisions if one party acted unreasonably in refusing to settle. This principle was first articulated in *Calderbank v Calderbank* [1975] 3 All ER 33 and remains an important tool in cost negotiations. However, irrelevant to our case as it will be discussed in relatability section.
6. **Delay or Procedural Issues**
In certain instances, **without prejudice** communications may be admissible to explain a **delay** in proceedings. For example, if one party delays filing or pursuing their case due to ongoing settlement negotiations, the court may allow evidence of those discussions to justify the delay.

³⁰ Can be deduced as a form of “unambiguous impropriety”, as in *Williams v Hull* (England and Wales High Court, Chancery Division, 19 November 2009) at [58] Arnold J, The judge referred to Rix LJ in *Savings & Investment Bank Ltd v Fincken* (England and Wales Court of Appeal, Civil Division, 14 November 2003) at [57] *when he said that it was not an abuse of the without prejudice privilege to tell the truth even if it is inconsistent with your pleaded case*. That paragraph of *Fincken* was approved by Lord Brown in *Bradford and Bingley plc v Rashid* [2006] Weekly Law Reports 2066 at paragraph 65; Judgment of the House of Lords of the United Kingdom delivered 12 July 2006, See *Woodward v Santander United Kingdom plc* [2010] Industrial Relations Law Reports 834; Decision of the Employment Appeal Tribunal of England and Wales delivered 2010.; Edward William Phipson. *Phipson on Evidence*, eighteenth edition. London: Sweet & Maxwell Ltd., December 2013, Pp. 111-112.

This exception ensures that the procedural fairness of the case is not undermined by settlement attempts³¹.

7. Reasonableness of a Settlement

When there is a dispute about the **reasonableness** of a settlement offer, **without prejudice** communications may be admitted to demonstrate whether the parties acted reasonably during settlement discussions. This can arise when assessing whether one party unreasonably rejected an offer, thereby impacting decisions on costs, as seen in case **Muller v Linsley & Mortimer [1994] EWCA Civ 39**³²: which highlighted that "without prejudice" protection can be lifted when it becomes clear that one party is abusing the process of settlement negotiations. If an unreasonable offer is made as part of such abusive conduct, the court may allow the disclosure of the communication to avoid injustice. "The plaintiffs cannot both assert the reasonableness of the settlement and claim privilege for the documents through which it was reached. The Court allowed the appeal"

³¹ O Michael O'Shea, "The Basics: What Does 'Without Prejudice' Mean and When Do I Need to Use It?" *Gowling WLG Website*, 25 June 2019.

³² Muller and another v Linsley and Mortimer [1994] England and Wales Court of Appeal (Civil Division) 39; Judgment delivered 30 November 1994.